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REPORT

on the activities of the research group „*Sentencing Human Smugglers in Hungary: Juridical Patterns and Algorithmic Potential*” of the Interdisciplinary Research Development and Innovation Excellence Centre at the University of Szeged between 2024 and 2026

Several research projects are currently underway within the Artificial Intelligence and Legal Order Research Group of the Interdisciplinary Research Development and Innovation Excellence Centre at the University of Szeged, examining the impact of technological development on the legal system as well as the opportunities it presents. As one of these projects, in early 2024 five of us – Prof. Dr. Krisztina Karsai, Prof. Dr. Zsanett Fantoly, Dr. habil. Péter Kovács, Dr. Andor Gál, and Dr. Bálint Csaba Kelemen – began examining the potential applications of artificial intelligence-based technologies within the criminal justice system. In the course of this research, we began exploring the possibilities of developing a rule-based artificial intelligence system capable of predicting the likely sanction in straightforward criminal cases. For this research, history itself provided an example of a “straightforward criminal case”: between 2021 and 2023, approximately 786 cases of human smuggling [Article 353 of Act C of 2012 on criminal Code (hereafter: *Criminal Code*)] were registered within the jurisdiction of the Szeged Regional Court (Fantoly–Gál–Kelemen 2025, 409). *According to our preliminary hypothesis, these cases exhibited highly similar criminological characteristics.* They therefore constitute a dataset of sufficient size from which information can be extracted and used as training data for a predictive system.

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Accordingly, we processed criminal cases on human smuggling that were filed with the Szeged District Court between 1 March 2022 and 30 June 2023. In the course of the research, we reviewed approximately 514 case files; however, the data from 34 cases could not be used due to data-entry errors or the absence of relevant documents from the files (Gál-Karsai 2025, 6). The data collected in this manner proved suitable for examining the feasibility of algorithmisation. Before proceeding, however, it was necessary to verify our hypothesis that these criminal cases were indeed straightforward in nature, both from substantive criminal law and procedural law perspectives. To this end, we conducted a thorough analysis of the criminal offence of human smuggling and sought to identify common patterns among the criminological characteristics of the cases. We also examined the criminal proceedings conducted in these matters, looking for recurring procedural features. In the present report, I aim to provide an account of these examinations and their findings.

1. Criminological Characteristics of the Cases Examined

Perhaps the most straightforward part of the research was the examination of the criminological characteristics, as it merely required a review of the available case files. In the course of this analysis, we found that the cases indeed exhibited a high degree of similarity. The commission of the offence is typically characterised by joint perpetration [Article 13 of Criminal Code], while the criminally relevant conduct of individual perpetrators varies due to the heterogeneous forms of assistance provided to irregular border-crossers:

- the recruiter enters into an agreement with the irregular border-crossers in their country of origin or in a country neighbouring Hungary regarding the organisation of their journey;

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- the organiser, acting in cooperation with the recruiter, typically coordinates – usually from outside the territory of Hungary – the activities of the so-called “walkers” waiting in a country neighbouring Hungary and the vehicle drivers who are typically present in Hungary; at the same time, the organiser maintains contact with the irregular border-crossers through mobile applications;
- the so-called “walker” personally establishes contact with the irregular border-crossers on the non-Hungarian side of the state border and escorts them to the border area, where the vehicle driver awaits them in order to transport them;
- the vehicle driver picks up the persons who have by that point crossed the state border unlawfully on the Hungarian side of the border at a pre-arranged location – typically a wooded, bush-covered, uninhabited area – and transports them further towards the Hungarian-Austrian border (Fantoly–Gál–Kelemen 2025, 410).

It was also established that the overwhelming majority of offenders were not Hungarian citizens and had no discernible connection to Hungary; their presence in the country was merely temporary and incidental, linked solely to the offence: Of the 541 defendants identified during the file review, only 28 were Hungarian citizens; thus, approximately 95% of the defendant population examined in the region consisted of foreign nationals (Fantoly–Gál–Kelemen 2025, 410). Taking into account the geographical location of Szeged, this finding is consistent with the data released by the National Commander of the Hungarian Prison Service on 16 November 2022, according to which foreign nationals accounted for approximately 90% of such offenders nationwide (Gál–Karsai 2024, 10).

It was also established that, in the vast majority of cases, the initiation of criminal proceedings was linked to the offenders being caught in the act. In all 480 cases that remained after data cleansing, the criminal proceedings were initiated when the police became aware of the offence during a roadside traffic inspection. Only a small proportion of offenders responded to apprehension with resistance; however, in such cases an additional related offence could typically be established, such as violence against a public official

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[Article 310 of Criminal Code], causing a road traffic accident [Article 235 of Criminal Code], or endangering road traffic [Article 234 of Criminal Code].

Finally, we also found that the objective gravity of the offence was determined primarily, and in a consistent manner, by the number of persons transported. In the cases examined, there were 9 instances in which the perpetrator provided assistance to only a single person, while two case files involved as many as 53 irregular border-crossers. The average number of persons transported was 12.

2. Substantive Criminal Law Characteristics of Human Smuggling

On the basis of the findings above, it could be concluded that the criminological characteristics of the cases exhibited a very high degree of similarity, thus confirming our initial hypothesis. We then examined whether the criminal law classification of these acts was likewise uniform and could indeed be regarded as straightforward. After all, sentencing can only be meaningfully analysed if the legal classification of the conduct is correct in every case. On this purpose, a detailed analysis of the statutory description of human smuggling was required, for which we have analysed the available legal literature and the historical legal norms and their current counterparts too.

After this we have found out, that the first historical precursor of human smuggling became part of Hungarian criminal law in 1948 under the designation “provisions on the unlawful use of passports and unlawful border crossing” [Article 48 of Act XLVIII of 1948]. The rationale for its introduction was that, in the legislator’s view, the sanctions imposed for abetting unlawful border crossing were not sufficiently severe, and it also aimed to exclude the possibility of mitigation (Gál–Karsai 2025, 8). Under the designation “human smuggling,” the offence first appeared in Act V of 1961, with the important difference that the basic statutory definition already included the element of providing assistance on a commercial basis [Article 204 of Act V of 1961]. Offenders engaging in one-off act were therefore

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punishable as abettors of unlawful border crossing [Article 203 of Act V of 1961]. In 1978, the requirement of commercial basis was replaced by the element of obtaining financial gain, in order to simplify evidentiary requirements. Later, in 1990, unlawful border crossing was reclassified as a petty offence, except in cases involving armed commission. As a consequence, a privileged form of human smuggling emerged, linked to the petty-offence version of unlawful border crossing. Finally, in 2002, with the abolition of the offence of armed unlawful border crossing, the statutory description took its present form: the basic offence no longer includes the element of financial gain, providing assistance to multiple persons became a qualified form as a statutory unity (Gál–Karsai 2025, 8-11).

Under the current legal regulation, human smuggling is therefore committed by anyone who provides aid to another person for crossing state borders in violation of the relevant statutory provisions [Article 353 of Criminal Code]. Through the changes outlined above, the legislator effectively established the punishability of act with a sui generis abetting character, since the act of a person crossing the Hungarian border only qualifies as a criminal offence if it is carried out by circumventing the border closure [Article 352/A. § of Criminal Code]; in other cases, it constitutes a petty offence. According to judicial practice, assistance may be carried out through active act or, where the offender has a duty to prevent it, through passive act as well. Active act may be either physical or psychological in nature; the requirement is that the conduct must facilitate the border crossing (Gál–Karsai 2025, 13).

The offence may be committed by anyone; however, in the cases examined, we encountered female offenders in only four instances, while proceedings were predominantly initiated against male offenders aged between 25 and 40. It is also worth noting that the offenders were nationals of as many as 48 different countries. Since anyone who provides assistance is considered a principal offender, joint-perpetration is of the greatest relevance; in the cases analysed, we encountered other forms of perpetration in only four instances. Nevertheless, most proceedings were conducted against a single defendant, given that judicial practice establishes joint-perpetration even where a particular offender cannot be identified, but their

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involvement can be traced (Gál–Karsai 2025, 16). It should also be noted that in the course of human smuggling offences, the full network could not be uncovered during the period under review, partly due to a lack of material resources available to the authorities and partly because the necessary forms of cross-border law enforcement cooperation did not take place (Gál–Karsai 2024, 9).

Within the sphere of substantive criminal law, it was also necessary to examine the issue of unity and multiplicity of offences. In this regard, it should be recalled that, of the 480 cases analysed, 471 involved the transportation of more than one irregular border-crosser; nevertheless, human smuggling was not classified as a multiple-count offence in a single case. The reason for this is that, since 2002, providing assistance to multiple persons has constituted a qualifying circumstance [Article 353 of Criminal Code], thereby creating a statutory unity of offence. Consequently, the number of counts is determined not by the number of persons transported, but rather by the number of borders crossed. (Gál–Karsai 2024, 17).

On the basis of the foregoing, the uniformity of the cases was evident not only in the nature of the act but also in its substantive legal classification. There were only five cases in which joint-perpetration could not be established, and only nine cases in which assistance was provided to a single person. *From a substantive criminal law perspective, the cases may therefore be regarded as straightforward, as the overwhelming majority involved the offence of human smuggling committed as joint-perpetrators and by providing assistance to multiple persons.*

3. Procedural Characteristics of Criminal Proceedings for Human Smuggling

Following the examination of the substantive criminal law issues, our research group also analysed the cases from the perspective of the complexity of the criminal proceedings conducted. In this context, we examined the characteristics of the investigation and the

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execution of sentences, as well as the proceedings before both the first-instance and second-instance courts, by processing the data gathered from the cases and interpreting the legal norms.

3.1. Characteristics of the Investigation

In the cases examined, no complex investigative measures were required. The fact-finding activities followed two principal directions:

- The primary focus of evidence gathering was the vehicle driver caught in the act, against whom charges were brought in every case. The suspect's interrogation largely determined the course of the proceedings, as a confession typically led the prosecution to initiate immediate summary procedure [Chapter XCVIII of Act XC of 2017 on Criminal Procedure (hereafter: *Code of Criminal Procedure*)]. In addition, without exception, two illegal immigrants were interviewed regarding the circumstances of the transportation. Following their interviews, they became subject to immigration proceedings and shortly thereafter left the territory of Hungary.
- Another important aspect of the investigations was the identification of the owner of the vehicle used for transporting the migrants. Owing to mechanisms of cooperation within the European Union, this did not present significant difficulties even when foreign individuals or entities were involved (Fantoly–Gál–Kelemen 2025, 410).

It should also be noted that in none of the cases did the investigation aim to identify the recruiter, organiser, or so-called “walker” involved in the smuggling operation. Likewise, no evidence was gathered concerning the circumstances under which the transported persons crossed the border, even though the content of the recorded statements could have provided reasonable grounds to infer the commission of the offence of unlawful crossing of the border barrier [Article 352/A of Criminal Code]. A common feature of the cases we examined was that, after being informed of their right not to incriminate [Article 7 of Code of Criminal

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Procedure] themselves, the witnesses generally refrained from making statements regarding the circumstances of their own border crossing.

Finally, a further common characteristic of criminal proceedings concerning human smuggling relates to coercive measures deprive personal freedom [Chapter XLV of Code of Criminal Procedure]. These cases were almost invariably “custodial cases,” in which the defendant's arrest was ordered. This circumstance, combined with the defendants’ frequent lack of proficiency in the Hungarian language, resulted in the near-universal involvement of defence counsel throughout the proceedings (Fantoly–Gál–Kelemen 2025, 411).

3.2. Characteristics of the First- and Second-Instance Criminal Proceedings

In the cases examined, the prosecution quickly recognised that the exceptionally high caseload could be reduced through the use of the specific procedure of immediate summary procedure. Accordingly, charges were brought in 249 cases under the rules governing this specific procedure, while 230 cases were conducted in accordance with the general procedural rules. Examples of circumstances justifying the omission of the expedited specific procedure and the filing of charges within the framework of ordinary proceedings included cases where the human smuggler identified the person who had commissioned the offence, where the acquisition of information from a foreign authority was time-consuming, or where one of the aggravated forms of human smuggling required more detailed evidentiary examination (Fantoly–Gál–Kelemen 2025, 411).

The special procedural rules governing direct referral to trial were applied in practice in almost every case, contributing significantly to the timely completion of proceedings and thereby helping to prevent any further increase in the caseload.

- In every case, the prosecution ensured that the defence was granted the right to inspect the case file prior to trial by informing defence counsel of this opportunity alongside the summons [Article 726 of Code of Criminal Procedure].

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- The courts also consistently complied with the rules governing judicially authorised coercive measures affecting personal liberty. Whenever, for any reason, the trial could not be conducted, the courts ruled on the issue of the coercive measure – which, by operation of law, ceased to have effect in such circumstances – in accordance with the provisions of the Code of Criminal Procedure [Article 725]. Similarly, a decision on this matter was rendered whenever the case file had to be returned to the prosecution because the conditions for applying the special procedure were not met [Article 727 of Code of Criminal Procedure].

During the evidentiary phase, particular significance was attached to the defendant's confession. Although no preparatory session is held in proceedings involving direct referral to trial, there was no obstacle to accepting a confession and dispensing with further evidence where the statutory requirements were satisfied. Consequently, a full evidentiary hearing was conducted only when the defendant advanced a substantive defence, which was typically aimed at avoiding the confiscation of property (Fantoly–Gál–Kelemen 2025, 411).

We have found out, that of the 480 processed cases, appeals against the first-instance judgment were lodged with the Szeged Regional Court in 317 cases. This included 181 cases arising from proceedings conducted under the immediate summary procedure and 136 cases adjudicated under the general procedural framework. Of these appellate remedies, 109 were filed by the defence, 40 sought a more severe sanction, and 172 involved opposing interests between the parties. In 225 cases, the appeal challenged only the sanction imposed or ancillary rulings, including, in numerous instances, the failure to apply the so-called “half-time rule” [Article 38 of Criminal Code]. By contrast, acquittal of the defendant was sought in only 94 cases. In these second-instance proceedings, we also examined the issue of procedural simplicity and its impact on sentencing. In this respect, only minor practical difficulties were identified.

- One issue that arose was whether the remaining parts of the first-instance judgment became partially final when the defence appeal challenged only the confiscation

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order. An examination of the rules governing scope of review revealed that, although the legislator prescribes a limited scope of review where a party appeals only against a preventive measure, the casuistic structure of the Code of Criminal Procedure nevertheless requires the review of all principal questions of criminal liability, with the exception of well-substantiated being of the judgement [Article 590 of Code of Criminal Procedure]. Consequently, it is difficult to envisage a situation in which modification of the principal criminal law issues would be excluded, provided that such modification remains within the limits imposed by the prohibition of reformatio in peius.

- We also examined the factors underlying the fact that, of the 283 second-instance decisions, the Szeged Regional Court rendered 52 in a panel session, 226 at a public session, and only 5 at a full appellate trial, despite the fact that the majority of appeals could have been adjudicated in panel session. In this regard, it was established that public sessions were requested primarily by defence counsel, partly for tactical litigation purposes and partly to promote the principles of immediacy and orality. We also found that the three-month procedural time limit prescribed by the Code of Criminal Procedure [Article 730] was exceeded in 117 cases, representing 53% of the relevant proceedings; however, this delay had no procedural consequences.
- With regard to second-instance judgements, the calculation of criminal procedural costs gave rise to recurring difficulties. Of the 98 decisions modifying the first-instance judgment, 67 altered only the amount of the procedural costs. Consistent judicial practice indicated that the basis for such modifications was typically an incorrect legal basis used when determining those costs. The underlying cause of these errors appeared to lie in the “analogue” nature of case administration and record-keeping, an area that clearly requires substantial development and modernisation in the future. (Fantoly–Gál–Kelemen 2025, 414-416).

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On the basis of the foregoing, our hypothesis concerning the simplicity and uniformity of these cases was also confirmed with respect to the procedural characteristics of the criminal proceedings. Investigations focused on only a narrow segment of the factual circumstances – namely, the forms of act defined by the criminological characteristics outlined above – after which the court proceedings were predominantly characterised by the use of special procedures designed to expedite adjudication. Consequently, from a criminal procedure perspective as well, these cases appear suitable for examining the feasibility of algorithmisation.

4. External Factors Shaping the Proceedings

As the final stage of our research, we also reviewed the external factors that shaped these criminal proceedings, in particular the measures adopted by the government to accelerate proceedings and to address the problems caused by the rapid growth of the prison population, by interpreting the legal norms and their explanatory notes. These external influences were most clearly reflected in the pattern of appeals. Initially, appeals were predominantly defence-oriented and included both challenges to the finding of guilt and appeals directed against the sanction imposed. This situation changed following a professional directive issued by the Office of the Prosecutor General, which instructed prosecutors to seek a more severe sentence on appeal irrespective of the type or severity of the sanction imposed at first instance. As a result, from late autumn 2022 onwards, appeals concerning sanctions and involving opposing interests became commonplace; unsurprisingly, requests for increased severity were typically met with corresponding requests for mitigation from the defence. This development imposed a considerable additional workload on the Szeged Regional Court. Meaningful relief came only with the entry into force of Decree No. 148/2023 (IV. 27.) (hereinafter: *Decree*). The Decree introduced the possibility of reintegration custody, which shifted the interests of the parties towards the swift conclusion of proceedings. Consequently,

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after April 2023, appeals became rare, and in 38 cases previously filed appellate remedies were withdrawn (Fantoly–Gál–Kelemen 2025, 415). All of this clearly demonstrates that the course of the criminal proceedings was significantly influenced by external factors from two distinct directions.

- In response to the growing prevalence of human smuggling, the prosecution sought to rely on the deterrent effect of criminal punishment. This approach manifested itself in the proposal of increasingly severe penalties and in the routine lodging of appeals against sanctions considered insufficiently harsh. However, this response proved ineffective, as the continued inability to identify and dismantle the underlying criminal networks allowed further offences to be committed on an ongoing basis.
- At the same time, the steadily increasing number of convicted offenders placed a considerable burden on the prison system. The legislator responded by introducing the institution of (atipic) reintegration custody. Despite its name, (atipic) reintegration custody is not, in substance, a form of custody; rather, it constitutes a special mechanism resembling the suspension of the execution of a sentence. A person convicted of human smuggling who has been sentenced to a term of imprisonment and, pursuant to the mandatory provisions of the Criminal Code [Article 60], has also been expelled from Hungary, may request to serve the sentence in his or her country of origin. In such cases, the expulsion order is executed before the custodial sentence, and the convicted person is required to leave the territory of Hungary within 72 hours. In contrast to the policy of seeking harsher punishments, this measure proved effective in reducing both the judicial caseload and the prison population. A significant number of convicted offenders soon availed themselves of this opportunity, and, together with the decline in migratory pressure, this ultimately led to the end of the overwhelming influx of human smuggling cases (Gál–Karsai 2025, 14).

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This atypical form of reintegration custody also gave rise to serious concerns regarding its compatibility with both the founding treaties of the European Union and secondary EU legislation. As a result, the European Commission initiated infringement proceedings against Hungary. According to the Commission's position, the quasi-release of offenders following the completion of criminal proceedings is incompatible with the EU requirement that sanctions be effective, proportionate, and dissuasive. Furthermore, the absence of any mechanism for monitoring compliance while offenders remain abroad may facilitate irregular migration within the territory of the European Union. In addition, the institution raises concerns with regard to the principle of non-discrimination, as it is applicable exclusively to foreign offenders and cannot be used in relation to Hungarian nationals (Gál–Karsai 2025, 14-15). These external influences, however, did not have any effective impact on the conduct of the proceedings themselves or on the length of the custodial sentences ultimately imposed by final judgments. *Accordingly, we concluded that they did not affect the fundamentally straightforward nature of the cases under examination.*

5. Summary

As the foregoing discussion demonstrates, our research group conducted a detailed examination of approximately 480 criminal cases filed between 1 March 2022 and 30 June 2023 in order to determine whether the information contained in these case files could serve as training data for an algorithm capable of predicting likely sanctions in straightforward criminal cases. The findings confirmed all of our preliminary assumptions and hypotheses, thereby providing a solid foundation for the development of such an algorithm. Our future work will therefore focus on the design and refinement of this predictive model. In particular, we intend to examine the explanatory power that the algorithm is able to identify with respect to individual sentencing decisions and sanctioning outcomes.

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